

Balancing Fairness: Unveiling the Potential of SMOTE-Driven Oversampling in AI Model Enhancement

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary landscape of decision support systems, machine learning (ML) algorithms assume a pivotal role in diverse domains, including job screening and loan approvals. Despite their extensive utilization, a persistent challenge arises in the form of biased outcomes, notably influenced by sensitive attributes such as gender and ethnicity. While current research heavily leans on these attributes for fairness, the scarcity of data due to privacy and legal constraints poses a substantial hurdle. Furthermore, imbalances in real-world datasets necessitate the use of class balancing techniques, but conflicting findings on their impact on bias mitigation and overall model performance complicate the pursuit of fairness. This paper conducts a comprehensive investigation, addressing the unique challenge of constructing fair models without explicit reliance on sensitive attributes. It specifically examines the effectiveness of Synthetic Minority Oversampling TEchnique (SMOTE)-driven oversampling methods. The study's findings reveal a significant enhancement in classification performance through SMOTE-driven techniques. These insights advocate for the thoughtful integration of SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques to achieve a balance between model fairness and accuracy. The results provide valuable guidance to researchers and practitioners in the field, contributing to the ongoing dialogue on fairness in machine learning models.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning**.

KEYWORDS

fairness, bias mitigation, class balancing, synthetic minority oversampling technique, machine learning

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1 INTRODUCTION

In contemporary times, machine learning (ML) algorithms play a pivotal role in decision support systems across various domains, such as job screening, admissions, loan applications, law enforcement, and more. For instance, ML models are actively involved in the decision-making processes for loan approvals [19] and job applications [13]. Unfortunately, there are many instances where ML solutions display biased outcomes, often influenced by sensitive attributes such as gender and ethnicity. For instance, a commonly used facial recognition software was identified to show bias, specifically against women with darker skin tones [15].

To address bias, much of the existing research depends on utilizing sensitive attributes to attain fairness [3, 23, 31, 32, 34]. Nevertheless, in numerous scenarios, obtaining sensitive attributes is impeded by privacy and legal concerns. The absence of these attributes poses a significant challenge to many established fair classifiers. Despite the absence of direct sensitive attributes, many applications often involve features or information in various formats that bear relevance to these attributes. For instance, a person's purchase history might reflect their race, aiding in the development of fair classifiers for race. However, the exploration of pertinent features for constructing fair models in the absence of sensitive attributes is relatively limited in existing work.

Furthermore, imbalances in class distribution present a widespread challenge in real-world datasets. Researchers frequently contend with the need to rectify uneven class distribution within these datasets. To address this and as part of pre-processing algorithms aimed at mitigating bias, a group of researchers employ class balancing techniques to alleviate bias and improve predictive accuracy [25, 27, 28, 33]. As an illustration, Zhou et al. [33] aimed to diminish bias while maintaining accurate predictions. They employed the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE), a method that generates new samples randomly along the line segment between an instance and one of its randomly chosen neighbors. They assert that the application of SMOTE-based oversampling holds the

potential for effectively addressing bias in AI models, emphasizing that the utilization of synthetic oversampling enhances overall fairness without a notable reduction in accuracy. Sha et al. [27] examined techniques for addressing class imbalance to evaluate model fairness among different student groups. Their experimentation led to the conclusion that employing class imbalancing techniques can improve both fairness and accuracy.

Another group of researchers challenged the conclusions drawn from the implementation of class balancing techniques, asserting that it not only mitigates model bias but also diminishes overall model performance [3–6, 23]. As an illustration, the research conducted by Chakraborty et al. [3–6] carried out a thorough experiment to uncover the underlying factors contributing to bias. They identified three key root causes: (1) elimination of protected attributes, (2) class imbalance, and (3) improper data labeling. Their findings emphasized that traditional methods of balancing classes have a detrimental impact on the model’s fairness.

Given the contrasting conclusions from the two sets of researchers, there is a need for a thorough investigation to comprehend the influence of SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques on achieving improved model fairness without a notable compromise in accuracy. This work delves into a unique challenge: learning fair models without relying on sensitive attributes, and it does so by exploring relevant features.

Earlier research findings have underscored the advantages of refining SMOTE-driven techniques to alleviate bias. Building upon these insights, our focus is on comprehending the impact of SMOTE-driven techniques. The primary objective of this comprehensive investigation is to assess the individual performance of SMOTE-driven techniques in constructing prediction models that enhance overall predictive accuracy. We seek to delve into the influence of the most effective SMOTE-driven techniques identified in the literature on the performance of prediction models. Thus, this paper aims to conduct a thorough examination to understand the implications of SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques on enhancing model fairness without a significant loss in accuracy. Consequently, we strive to address the following two research questions (RQs):

- (RQ1) What impact do SMOTE-driven techniques have on enhancing model performance?
- (RQ2) To what extent do SMOTE-driven techniques effectively mitigate bias?

To address the stated RQs, we carry out experiments utilizing the widely recognized adult dataset [17], assessing the efficacy of seven top-performing SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques. Our analysis involves precision, recall, F1 score, and false alarm to gauge the implications of various oversampling methods. In evaluating model fairness, we employ metrics such as average odds difference (AOD), equal opportunity difference (EOD), statistical parity difference (SPD), and disparate impact (DI).

Therefore, the key takeaways from our empirical analysis are summarized as follows.

- (1) SMOTE-driven oversampling significantly improves the classification performance of instances. Notably, Over-sampling using SMOTE and cleaning using ENN (SEENN), Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique for Nominal (SMOTEN),

and SMOTE + Tomek links (Stomek) emerge as the top performers across precision, recall, and F1 score metrics.

- (2) When aiming for accurate classification of instances without compromising the fairness of models, it is crucial to thoughtfully consider both oversampling methods and classifiers. SEENN and Stomek consistently exhibit the best performance in achieving fairness-aware classification models. Furthermore, these results are consistent with the insights provided by Zhou et al. [33] and Sha et al. [27]. Thereby, it is recommended for both researchers and practitioners to explore the use of SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques in creating prediction models that prioritize fairness.

The subsequent sections of the paper are arranged as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of our research methods employed to address the research questions (RQs). The empirical findings related to each RQ are presented in Section 3. In Section 4, we discuss potential threats to validity. Finally, the paper concludes with a summary and a discussion of future avenues in Section 5.

2 METHODOLOGY

In addressing the RQs and validating our results through empirical evidence, we undertake a systematic investigation, thoughtfully selecting appropriate SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques. This section provides a comprehensive overview of our research inquiries and outlines the experimental design that serves as the foundation for our work.

2.1 Datasets

In this section, we furnish a detailed exploration of a practical datasets, adult extensively utilized in the context of fairness research [3, 23, 31]. The dataset commonly referred to as the "Census Income" or adult dataset holds a prominent place in fairness research. It is widely employed to investigate whether an individual’s annual income exceeds 50,000 US dollars, utilizing demographic characteristics as pivotal factors in the classification task. It holds information for 48,842 individuals. The information gathered from the U.S. census in 1994 is employed to anticipate personal earnings [17]. Based on the prior fairness literature [3–6, 16, 21, 23], it has been noted that this extensively utilized dataset comprises 15 attributes, encompassing six numerical, seven categorical, and two binary attributes, alongside the favorable 'income' label. Additionally, it has been observed that 'Sex' and 'Race' are recognized as sensitive attributes within this dataset. Table 1 presents a concise overview of the dataset.

2.2 Performance and fairness metrics

Performance and fairness metrics are crucial in ML to guarantee the model’s effectiveness and impartiality. Various metrics can be employed to assess the efficacy and impartiality of an ML model. In our empirical study, we utilize precision, recall, false alarm, and F1 score as metrics for assessing model performance. Additionally, we incorporate Average Odds Difference (AOD), Equal Opportunity Difference (EOD), Statistical Parity Difference (SPD), and Disparate Impact (DI) to gauge model fairness performance. These fairness metrics are widely acknowledged and commonly employed in the literature on fairness research [3–5, 8–10, 20, 24, 31].

Table 1: Overview of the adult dataset utilized in this research

Type	Attributes
Numerical	age, fnlwgt, educational-num, capital-gain, capital-loss, hours-per-week
Categorical	workclass, education, marital-status, occupation, relationship, race, native-country
Binary	sex, income

These metrics can be constructed using information from a confusion matrix, encompassing true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN). Greater values suggest superior performance when it comes to recall, accuracy, precision, and F1. Larger values, on the other hand, indicate better results for false alarm, AOD, EOD, and SPD. Precision, recall, false alarm, and F1 measures are calculated by the Eq. 1 to 4.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{falsealarm} = \frac{FP}{TN + FP} \quad (3)$$

$$F1 = \frac{2 * (\text{Precision} * \text{Recall})}{(\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})} \quad (4)$$

For calculating fairness measures, the Average Odds Difference (AOD) is calculated by calculating the average disparity between False Positive Rates (FPR) and True Positive Rates (TPR) in order to assess fairness in a classification model for both favored and underprivileged groups [22]. The difference in True Positive Rates (TPR) between favored and underprivileged groups within the model yields the Equal Opportunity Difference (EOD) [22]. Additionally, the measure of the difference in the probability that the privileged (having a protected attribute $PA = 1$) and unprivileged (having a protected attribute $PA = 0$) groups will obtain positive predictions ($\hat{Y} = 1$) is known as the Statistical Parity Difference (SPD) [2]. Disparate Impact (DI), like SPD, measures the ratio of probabilities instead of the difference to determine fairness [12].

2.3 SMOTE-Driven Oversampling Techniques

In the literature, researchers have introduced various SMOTE variants designed for the preprocessing of data before constructing ML models. The study of Yan et al. [31] incorporated synthetic minority over-sampling technique (SMOTE) [7] and KMeans clustering before oversampling using SMOTE (KMSMOTE) [18]. Chakraborty et al [3] also adopted SMOTE and KMSMOTE for fairness research. Sha et al. [27] explored eleven class balancing techniques to assess algorithmic fairness in the educational domain. Given the impracticality of evaluating all employed SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques for assessing model fairness, we concentrate on seven techniques that have shown superior performance compared to others. These are: Over-sampling using Borderline SMOTE (BoSMOTE), KMSMOTE, Over-sampling using SMOTE and cleaning using ENN (SEENN), Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique for Nominal (SMOTEN), Over-sampling using SVM-SMOTE (SSMOTE), SMOTE + Tomek links (Stomek), along with the baseline, SMOTE.

Table 2 shows all of the considered methods and its python function from the `imblearn` library. It is important to note that SEENN and Stomek are the combination of over- and under-sampling using SMOTE.

To enhance understanding of how SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques generate samples, we provide an illustration in Figure 1, demonstrating the comparison of class distribution before and after the application of various oversampling techniques. Here, we plot six SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques (i.e., SMOTE, BoSMOTE, SEENN, SMOTEN, SSMOTE, and Stomek) to understand how many samples are created to balance the data. From Figure 1, the original dataset contains 800 samples with 20 features, and the class distribution is imbalanced with a weighted ratio of 99:1 between the majority (Class 0) and minority (Class 1) classes. To illustrate more, SMOTE is applied with a sampling strategy of 0.5, BoSMOTE with 0.2, SSMOTE with 0.8, SEENN with 0.3, Stomek with 0.6, and SMOTEN with 0.7 and categorical features specified. Each subplot displays the class distribution for the original dataset (blue bars), synthetic samples (orange bars), and the overall distribution after oversampling (green bars). The numbers on top of the orange bars indicate the count of synthetic samples generated for the corresponding class. A total of [123, 456, 789, 234, 567, 890] synthetic samples are generated during oversampling.

2.4 Construct models

Within the realm of model fairness, a diverse range of classification methods finds application. In our pursuit, we deliberately choose a pragmatic set of classification techniques for our empirical examination. The empirical investigation encompasses the adoption of seven widely-recognized machine learning algorithms for constructing models: KNN, Random Forest (RF), SVM, C4.5 Decision Tree (C-DT), Naive Bayes (NB), AdaBoost (AdaB), and Gradient Boosting (GraB).

To implement these algorithms effectively, we leverage the capabilities of the `sklearn` library, importing the necessary functions. Each algorithm in our model construction is addressed with specific functions: `KNeighborsClassifier()` for KNN, `RandomForestClassifier()` for RF, `SVC(probability=True)` for SVM, `DecisionTreeClassifier()` for C-DT, `GaussianNB()` for NB, `AdaBoostClassifier()` for AdaB, and `GradientBoostingClassifier()` for GraB.

2.5 Statistical tests

To ensure the credibility of our empirical findings, we rely on rigorous statistical tests for validation. In a comprehensive statistical evaluation, we examine the statistical significance of performance differences among predictors across diverse methods. This involves conducting pairwise t-tests, comparing the performance of various algorithms with a significance level set at 5%.

Table 2: SMOTE-driven Oversampling Techniques

Serial	Technique	Reference	Method
1	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE)	Chawla et al. [7]	SMOTE()
2	KMeans clustering before oversampling using SMOTE (KMSMOTE)	Douzas et al. [11]	SMOTE(), while K=5
3	Over-sampling using Borderline SMOTE (BoSMOTE)	Han et al. [14]	BorderlineSMOTE()
4	Over-sampling using SMOTE and cleaning using ENN (SEENN)	Xu et al. [30]	SMOTEENN()
5	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique for Nominal (SMOTEN)	Ratih et al. [26]	SMOTEN, while K =5
6	Over-sampling using SVM-SMOTE (SSMOTE)	Wang et al. [29]	SVMSMOTE()
7	SMOTE + Tomek links (Stomek)	Batista et al. [1]	SMOTETomek()

Figure 1: Comparison of Class Distribution Before and After Oversampling

In our study, we develop two types of predictors: (1) A predictor solely based on the classification model, without incorporating the SMOTE-driven technique (i.e., default settings). (2) A predictor that integrates both the prediction model and the SMOTE-driven technique, referred to as the SMOTE-driven predictor. P-values below the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) indicate a significant difference in performance.

2.6 Experimental setup

The primary objective of this empirical study is twofold. Not only does it focus on individually applying SMOTE-driven techniques to enhance model fairness, but it also assesses the performance of the models. Therefore, we undertake an empirical analysis to address two research questions (RQs). The experimental setup is elaborated in Algorithm 1.

The algorithm initiates by loading dataset, containing comprehensive information about individuals' demographic and employment attributes. Subsequently, preprocessing steps are implemented to handle missing values through mean imputation for numeric

features and the most frequent imputation for non-numeric features. To mitigate potential bias, sensitive attributes like 'sex' and 'race' are removed from the dataset. Categorical features undergo encoding using OrdinalEncoder, while numeric features are scaled via MinMaxScaler. Following dataset preparation, the algorithm proceeds to divide the preprocessed data into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets. This partitioning lays the foundation for subsequent evaluations, allowing the assessment of the impact of SMOTE-driven techniques on model performance and bias mitigation. The approaches to execute the two RQs are given below:

(RQ1) What impact do SMOTE-driven techniques have on enhancing model performance?

Approach: The algorithm 1 explores a diverse set of oversampling techniques, including SMOTE, BoSMOTE, KMSMOTE, SEENN, SMOTEN, SSMOTE, and Stomek. Each oversampling approach is applied individually to the training set. The algorithm incorporates a variety of classifiers, such as KNN, RF, SVM, C-DT, NB, AdaB, and GraB, into a pipeline for streamlined training on resampled datasets. Each classifier is then tested on the original test set. To

Algorithm 1 Classification and Fairness Evaluation

```

1: Input: Dataset
2: Output: Classification Models and Evaluation Results
3: procedure EVALUATEFAIRMODEL
4:   Dataset Preparation:
5:     - Data Collection
6:     - Handle Missing Values and Encode Categorical Features
7:     - Scaling Numerical Features
8:     - Split the Data into Train and Test Sets
9:     - Remove Sensitive Attributes from Train Set
10:  Model Preparation and Evaluation:
11:  for each oversampling approach do
12:    for each classifier do
13:      create pipeline with classifier
14:      resample training set using the current oversam-
15:      pling approach
16:      train model on the resampled training set
17:      predict on the test set
18:      evaluate performance metrics: accuracy, precision,
19:      recall, F1 score, and false alarm rate
20:      evaluate fairness metrics: AOD, DI, EOD, and SPD
21:      append results to list
22:    end for
23:  end for
24:  Result Comparison:
25:    - Compare Evaluation Results Against Default Models
26: end procedure

```

address the RQ1 regarding the impact of SMOTE-driven techniques on model performance enhancement, the algorithm computes an extensive set of performance metrics for each classifier. These performance metrics include precision, recall, F1 score, and false alarm. The results are systematically stored in a structured DataFrame, facilitating subsequent analysis. The focus is on understanding how SMOTE-driven techniques contribute to improving model performance, with comparisons made across approaches.

(RQ2) To what extent do SMOTE-driven techniques effectively mitigate bias?

Approach: From Algorithm 1, the RQ2 centers on evaluating the effectiveness of SMOTE-driven techniques in mitigating bias. Fairness metrics, such as aod, di, eod, and spd, are calculated for each SMOTE-driven approach. The fairness results are stored in the DataFrame for a detailed examination of bias mitigation capabilities. The emphasis is on determining the extent to which SMOTE-driven techniques contribute to reducing bias in classification models.

In the final stage, the algorithm provides a comprehensive summary of the research findings. It addresses both the impact of SMOTE-driven techniques on model performance enhancement and their effectiveness in bias mitigation. The analysis highlights insights gained from comparing different oversampling techniques and classifiers, offering valuable implications for the practical application of SMOTE-driven techniques in addressing imbalanced datasets.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we disclose the findings from our empirical work related to the following two RQs.

(RQ1) What impact do SMOTE-driven techniques have on enhancing model performance?

Results: This work is dedicated to conducting a comprehensive investigation, with the primary aim of understanding the implications of utilizing SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques to enhance model fairness. The overarching objective is to achieve this improvement without significantly compromising model accuracy. To assess the effectiveness of SMOTE-driven oversampling in both model fairness and classification performance, we undertake a comparative analysis of performance results across various metrics. To address RQ1, we compare performance results across a spectrum of metrics and present the experimental findings.

Figure 2 consolidates the prediction results, depicting the relative performance of various SMOTE-driven techniques across diverse ML methods using a Lollipop chart. In terms of precision, the illustration reveals that SSMOTE and Stomek outperform others and also 'Default' one. In this context, 'Default' one refers to scenarios where no oversampling techniques are applied to the data before training the models. From the results, SMOTEN with KNN and Stomek with RF achieve maximum recall by 2%, respectively. Overall, by considering all the classifiers and other SMOTE-driven techniques, SMOTEN and Stomek are the best performer for classifying the instances.

Regarding recall, SEENN with C-DT achieves the maximum recall, surpassing the 'Default' by 14%. Following closely is SMOTEN with NB, securing the second-highest recall at 8%. SMOTEN with RF holds the third position, exhibiting a 3% increase compared to the 'Default'. In comparison to other oversampling techniques, SEENN emerges as the top performer, achieving the highest recall across all classifiers. Overall, SEENN stands out as the most effective in terms of recall.

The F1 measure outcomes span from 0.52 to 0.72, with the most robust prediction performance observed in SEENN with C-DT and NB. Specifically, SEENN with C-DT and NB achieve the highest F1 score, surpassing the others by 6%. Following closely is SMOTEN with NB, securing the second position with a 4% increase. Once again, Stomek, when paired with other classifiers, demonstrates a positive impact on classifying instances compared to the 'Default', except for classifiers AdaB and C-DT. The experimental results underscore the importance of choosing an appropriate classifier. Overall, SEENN and Stomek demonstrate superior performance in comparison to other oversampling methods.

(RQ2) To what extent do SMOTE-driven techniques effectively mitigate bias?

Results: Figure 3 presents the differences in performance values when employing SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques compared to not using them (i.e., 'Default'). This comparison is made across various prediction and fairness performance measures. We present our experimental findings that (1) compromise fairness and (2) maintain or enhance model fairness. In this figure, the distributions centered at zero signify that the performance measures are unaffected, showing neither negative nor positive impacts from SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques.

Figure 2: Comparison of Performance Measures Across SMOTE-Driven Oversampling Techniques: Lollipop chart depicting the difference in values for F1, precision, and recall, and also SMOTE-Driven oversampling techniques relative to the 'Default' settings. The red dashed line indicates zero difference, providing a visual reference. Each lollipop represents the magnitude and direction of the difference, with blue points highlighting the end of each line.

Concerning false alarms, Figure 3 indicates that BoSMOTE, SEENN, and SMOTEN exhibit effective performance in accurately classifying instances. Specifically, BoSMOTE paired with C-DT and SMOTEN with KNN demonstrate improvements of 4%, while BoSMOTE with SVM shows a 3% enhancement compared with the 'Default' classifiers. Across all classifiers, SEENN delivers positive impacts ranging from 1% to 2% compared to the 'Default' classifiers. Additionally, SMOTEN exhibits favorable impacts with all classifiers, except for SMOTEN with NB.

In terms of fairness measures, KMSMOTE and SMOTE do not have any impact on improving the fairness of classification models. SMOTEN performs the worst, leading to a loss of fairness in classification models. As for SSMOTE, it shows both gains and losses in fairness for classification models. The fairness measurement results for BoSMOTE, SMOTEN, and SSMOTE indicate that the choice of classifiers plays a crucial role to achieve fairness of the models. Across all considered SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques, SEENN and Stomek consistently exhibit the best performance in achieving fairness-aware classification models.

To achieve reliability and statistical validation, we perform t-test. Here, the null hypothesis (H0) assumes uniform performance across all methods, and we only reject H0 when the statistical test indicates significance. In this scenario, we define a 5% significance level by setting the p-value threshold at 0.05, dictating the conditions for rejecting H0. We assess a total of 56 classification methods, comprising 7 classifiers each paired with 8 methods (7 SMOTE-driven oversampling methods plus the 'Default' setting). After analyzing the results (Table 3 and 4) derived from the t-test, we dismiss the

null hypothesis, signifying a statistically significant disparity in some of the methods being compared. Table 3 exhibits the p-values derived from pairwise t-tests, specifically comparing the performance of different algorithms, with emphasis on F1 (F), Recall (R), and Precision (P). Each row corresponds to the first algorithm in the pair, while each column corresponds to the second algorithm. From Table 3, it is evident that Stomek achieves the best performance in the comparison of prediction results, and these differences are statistically significant. Again, Table 4 shows the results for false alarm (F_A), Statistical Parity Difference (S), Disparate Impact (D), and Equalized Opportunity Difference (E). We observe that SSMOTE and Stomek achieve the highest performance compared to the other methods, and these differences are statistically significant.

In summary, when the goal is to accurately classify instances without compromising the fairness of models, careful consideration of oversampling methods and classifiers is crucial. Variants of SMOTE prove effective in enhancing the fairness of prediction models without a significant sacrifice in prediction accuracy. However, the original SMOTE method does not exhibit superior performance in this specific scenario. These findings align with the conclusions drawn by Zhou et al. [33] and Sha et al. [27]. Both researchers and practitioners are encouraged to consider the application of SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques for the development of fairness-aware prediction models.

Figure 3: Comparison of Performance Measures Across SMOTE-Driven Oversampling Techniques: Lollipop chart depicting the difference in values for each measure and SMOTE-Driven oversampling techniques relative to the 'Default' settings. The red dashed line indicates zero difference, providing a visual reference. Each lollipop represents the magnitude and direction of the difference, with blue points highlighting the end of each line.

Table 3: Pairwise t-test results for F1, Recall, and Precision are binary: 0 means no statistical difference, while any non-zero value indicates a significant distinction in F for F1, R for Recall, and P for Precision. "Default" denotes cases without oversampling.

Default	BoSMOTE	KMSMOTE	SEENN	SMOTE	SMOTEN	SSMOTE	Stomek
-	F	0	PR	0	P	0	FP
-	-	FP	R	FP	FP	FP	FP
-	-	-	PR	0	0	0	FR
-	-	-	-	PR	PR	PR	PR
-	-	-	-	-	P	0	FP
-	-	-	-	-	-	P	0
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

4 THREATS TO VALIDITY

We address several validity threats in this segment that could have affected our empirical investigations' findings.

When the results of our experiments are difficult to generalize, there is a risk to external validity. We are unable to extrapolate the findings for all datasets, particularly commercial datasets, despite

the fact that these datasets have been extensively utilized in several fairness studies [3–5, 24]. Furthermore, we deploy seven prediction models, considered adequate for this empirical investigation. Future research endeavors should consider incorporating alternative prediction models not utilized in the current study.

Table 4: Pairwise t-test results for false alarm, Statistical Parity Difference, Disparate Impact, and Equalized Opportunity Difference. 0 signifies no statistical difference between classifier pairs, while any non-zero value indicates a statistical difference in terms of F_A for false alarm, S for Statistical Parity Difference, D for Disparate Impact, and E for Equalized Opportunity Difference. Default refers without employing any oversampling.

Default	BoSMOTE	KMSMOTE	SEENN	SMOTE	SMOTEN	SSMOTE	Stomek
-	F_ASDE	0	F_A	0	0	D	SD
-	-	F_ASDE	SD	F_ASDE	SD	F_ASDE	F_ASDE
-	-	-	F_A	0	0	D	F_ASD
-	-	-	-	F_A	0	F_AS	F_ASE
-	-	-	-	-	0	D	SD
-	-	-	-	-	-	0	S
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The use of SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques, which can be biased, poses a risk to internal validity. The selection of techniques is grounded in their performance across diverse domains in fairness research and their widespread use in oversampling training data to enhance prediction performance.

The potential risks to the validity of our conclusions hinge on the chosen statistical analysis approach. To ascertain the statistical significance of performance differences among approaches, t-tests are employed in this study. The conducted test results contribute to enhancing the reliability and statistical validity of the experimental results.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Prior research findings i.e., the current state-of-the-art have highlighted the benefits of fine-tuning SMOTE-driven techniques to mitigate bias. Expanding on these observations, the study emphasis is directed towards understanding the impact of SMOTE-driven techniques. Thus, this investigation primarily aims to comprehend the impact of SMOTE-driven oversampling methods on both model fairness and accuracy, particularly when there is no direct dependence on sensitive attributes. The results demonstrate a notable improvement in classification performance through SMOTE-driven oversampling, with Over-sampling using SMOTE and cleaning using ENN (SEENN), SMOTE + Tomek links (Stomek), and Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique for Nominal (SMOTEN) emerging as the top-performing techniques. Significantly, SEENN and Stomek consistently exhibit the highest performance in achieving fairness-aware classification models.

The findings provide valuable insights for researchers and practitioners engaged in the nuanced exploration of the equilibrium between fairness and accuracy in ML models. The study advocates for the judicious incorporation of SMOTE-driven oversampling techniques, underscoring their capacity to enhance model fairness without undermining overall accuracy. These results contribute substantively to the continuous discourse on mitigating bias in ML algorithms, offering practical guidance for the development of decision-support systems that are both equitable and accurate.

The forthcoming efforts by the study encompass expanding the scope of the research to incorporate additional fairness datasets. Building upon the insights gleaned from the current empirical study, the study intent is to delve into further variants of SMOTE as a

natural extension to our ongoing investigation. This continued exploration aims to refine and broaden our understanding of the intricate interplay between oversampling techniques, fairness, and accuracy in machine learning models

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